

Amputations on Demand: Why Body Integrity Dysphoria (BID) is Everybody's Problem

Abstract

Body Integrity Dysphoria (BID), despite its statistical rarity and apparent oddity, raises fundamental questions about dignity, autonomy, and moral responsibility that concern all individuals. This paper examines whether abstention—refusing to intervene for BID—is morally preferable to active intervention, by drawing a parallel with Medical Assistance in Dying (MAiD). Drawing from contemporary ethical debates on the permissibility of passive versus active euthanasia, the paper develops a philosophical argument comparing BID surgery to active euthanasia and the refusal of BID surgery to passive euthanasia. It applies the distinction between experiential and critical interests, as well as the role of available life paths in shaping well-being and personal narratives, to explore how moral responsibility should be understood in cases of BID. What is argued is that abstention is not neutrality but a form of action that carries the same moral weight as intervention while often being disguised as inaction. Both BID surgery and its refusal involve harm, but refusal unjustifiably prolongs suffering and erodes dignity. Respecting the wishes of individuals with BID is therefore not only a matter of clinical practice but also a test of whether dignity and autonomy are treated as universal values rather than selectively granted privileges.

Keywords: #BodyIntegrityDysphoria, #MedicalAssistanceInDying, #euthanasia, #autonomy, #dignity, #abstention, #inaction, #moralresponsibility, #suffering, #bioethics

Introduction

Body Integrity Dysphoria (BID) is added to the ICD-11 (World Health Organization, 2022) under code 6C21. The aetiology of the condition is complex and involves interacting neurological, psychological, and sociocultural components (Loriga, 2025d). It is marked by a persistent and intense desire for impairment (typically a fixed desire for a *specific* alteration of the body, most commonly the amputation of a defined healthy limb or, less frequently, paraplegia), although the ICD-11 refers to it as a desire for *disability*. These two concepts, although linked, do not necessarily overlap (for a putative differentiation between these two concepts, see, for example, Morris, 2001; Oliver, 1990, pp. 12–22; Shakespeare & Watson, 2001). For the BID case, disability and impairment can be considered as sitting at the two opposite ends of the

spectrum. As argued elsewhere (Loriga, 2025b), surgery can, in fact, enhance quality of life rather than result in disability. Despite ongoing discussions, there is currently no recognised therapeutic approach for treating BID. However, there is growing recognition within the medical community of the need for a surgical solution—amputation—to address the dysphoric state (Kasten, 2025). Despite these positive signals, which hint at a deeper understanding of the condition and its implications compared to a few years ago, amputation remains prohibited or unavailable in most Western jurisdictions (where the overwhelming majority of documented BID cases are reported) and is widely criticised as a form of care (Loriga, 2024). Although several factors contribute to the way individuals with BID navigate healthcare—including stigma, repeated negative encounters with clinicians, and the absence of any sanctioned or regulated treatment pathway—the restricted clinical access they face is one of the reasons many turn to unofficial or anonymous spaces. This has triggered a domino effect of unintended consequences that significantly affect how individuals with BID engage with healthcare systems and seek support:

1. The limited understanding of BID within the medical community compels many individuals to discover and make sense of their condition through unofficial channels, primarily online communities and forums.
2. These online environments, while offering validation and shared experiences, often operate outside the scope of clinical guidance, leaving little opportunity to communicate scientifically accurate or ethically grounded information to those affected—or who believe themselves to be affected.
3. As many of these communities are private, closed, and anonymous, they remain inaccessible to researchers and clinicians, contributing to a systematic underreporting of BID and a distorted understanding of its actual prevalence.
4. Experiences of misdiagnosis or dismissal by medical professionals further erode trust, fostering the belief among affected individuals that the medical establishment is either incompetent or hostile toward their condition.
5. This lack of trust, combined with unmet needs, has led to the growth of closed communities, DIY medical interventions, and even the emergence of black-market dynamics, all of which pose serious risks to health and safety.

The scope of this paper is not to address the social phenomena related to BID, such as the role of gated online communities of BID members, DIY interventions, or black-market dynamics. Instead, I argue that although BID may appear to be a medical oddity—statistically rare and ethically complex—it serves as a lens into broader systemic issues: namely, the belief within the medical world and bioethics discourse that abstention is less damaging than intervention (for example Brassington, 2020; Gillon, 1986; Loriga, 2025a, p. 114; Räsänen & Häyry, 2024; Riisfeldt, 2023).

To elaborate on this argument, I draw a parallel with Medical Assistance in Dying (MAiD)—comparison to gender dysphoria and gender-affirming care, although relevant, has been extensively explored elsewhere (Loriga, 2025c) and will therefore not be touched on here. The analogy proposed is the following: *BID surgery is to active euthanasia as refusing BID surgery is to passive euthanasia.*

“The distinction between active and passive euthanasia is thought to be crucial for medical ethics. The idea is that it is permissible, at least in some cases, to withhold treatment and allow a patient to die, but it is never permissible to take any direct action designed to kill the patient” (Rachels, 1975, p. 78)

While both ultimately accomplish the same end, the latter—passive euthanasia, that is *withhold treatment and allow a patient to die*—is often regarded as less morally problematic than the former—active euthanasia. Such a distinction, however, skews the focus of the practice by privileging methodology over the moral end, that is, preserving the patient's dignity and relieving suffering. On the contrary, the argument advanced here is that passive euthanasia—and, by analogy, the refusal to intervene in BID—is morally worse than active euthanasia, precisely because it prolongs suffering. The focus, as it will be argued, shall be on preserving and fostering the patient's dignity and respecting one's autonomy. Such respect lies in the recognition of one's enduring self in relation to the suffering they now inhabit, even when that suffering arises from a condition that presently alters their cognitive or emotional state.

“...the autonomy of the person of the lifetime deserves equal or more weight than a decision-making third party when the person of the moment lacks capacity to

make a healthcare decision... the pursuit of critical interests gives meaning to human life and is encoded in ADs to represent the whole person” (Hart, 2021, p. 2)

In this view and given that all beings are perishable and will inevitably face end-of-life stages, the preservation of personal dignity must be everybody's concern.

Today, many jurisdictions such as the Netherlands and Belgium recognise, for example, that chronic psychiatric suffering can, under strict conditions, warrant the same respect for bodily sovereignty as terminal physical illness (Bosma et al., 2024; De Hert & Van Assche, 2024; Dierickx et al., 2017; Verhofstadt et al., 2024). Such a recognition is a beacon of hope, warning that dignity is not reserved for those facing imminent death but extends to all individuals whose suffering severely undermines their capacity to live meaningfully.

Refusing to treat BID as a one-off anomaly and instead situating it within this broader ethical landscape forces a confrontation with a more fundamental question: Who ultimately holds the right to determine what may be done to a person's body when the source of suffering is not disease alone, but the unlivability of one's current state of embodiment?

What is Medical Assistance in Dying (MAiD)

The first step to take is a necessary clarification. This paper assumes that Medical Assistance in Dying (MAiD) is a legitimate medical intervention, not one to be excluded *a priori* on the basis of religious or metaphysical preconceptions, such as the Declaration on Euthanasia of May 5th, 1980, and later reiterated in Samaritanus Bonus (Congregation for the Doctrine of the Faith, 2020) or similar texts of either religious or secular origin.

“...no one is permitted to ask for this act of killing, either for himself or herself or for another person entrusted to his or her care, nor can he or she consent to it, either explicitly or implicitly. nor can any authority legitimately recommend or permit such an action. For it is a question of the violation of the divine law, an offense against the dignity of the human person, a crime against life, and an attack on humanity.” (Congregation for the Doctrine of the Faith, 1980)

MAiD, as it will be referred to throughout this paper, is defined by the Government of Canada as “...a process that allows someone who is found eligible to be able to receive assistance from a medical practitioner in ending their life.” (Government of Canada, 2016). This definition is adopted here for its clarity and recognisability within Anglophone bioethical and legal discourse. Given these premises, therefore, the ethical tension addressed here does not lie in the question of *whether* assisting someone to die is permissible. Instead, it lies in the methodological dimensions of such assistance. That is, the core of the medical and ethical debate concerns the *modes* through which such assistance is delivered.

There are various forms of MAiD, but they are commonly divided into two broad categories: euthanasia and physician-assisted suicide (PAS) across relevant literature (see, for example, Singer & Viens, 2009, pp. 71–78).

“...euthanasia is defined as a physician deliberately administering a lethal substance or carrying out an intervention to cause the death of a patient with decision-making capacity at the patient’s own voluntary request. Physician-assisted suicide refers to cases in which, at the voluntary request of a patient with decision-making capacity, a physician deliberately enables a patient to end his or her own life by prescribing or providing medical substances with the intent to bring about death.” (The World Medical Association, 2025)

Further distinctions are often drawn within euthanasia itself, particularly between active and passive forms. While active euthanasia is generally considered to directly cause the death of a patient through a specific act—such as a lethal injection, which is an act of *killing*—passive euthanasia involves withholding or withdrawing life-sustaining treatment, thereby *allowing* the patient to die. It should be noted, that this distinction is far from settled and remains the subject of a vivid moral debate (Brassington, 2020; Gesang, 2008; Rachels, 1975; Reichenbach, 1987).

The tension between the putative moral distinction between euthanasia and PAS, and between active and passive euthanasia—that is, *killing* versus *letting die*—rests on the assumption that abstention—*letting die*—is the lesser harm between the two (Foley, 1997) because “...is the condition, not the action of withdrawing treatment, that causes death...” and again “...A physician who performs euthanasia or assists in a suicide, by comparison, has

the death of the patient as his or her primary objective” (Singer & Viens, 2009, p. 73). To be clear, proponents of the doing–allowing distinction do not claim that a lesser harm occurs in cases of omission, but rather that the agent is considered less morally culpable when they allow a death than when they bring it about through a direct act. Even though autonomy is recognised as a critical element in patients' dignity, it shall not mean absolute self-determination, especially when social policies are involved (Callahan, 1992). Proponents, on the other hand, deny such distinction and see the two instances as equal (Angell, 1997; Brock, 1992; Brody, 1992).

The Illusion of Abstention

To fully understand why MAiD should be everyone's concern, and why, by the same token, BID as well, it is possible to propose the following postulate. If we say that harm exists—regardless of whether we treat harm as subjective or objective, and regardless of its specific form—we are already comparing it to other possible states, less harmful or non-harmful, which means harm must sit on a spectrum rather than exist in isolation.. This also means that such a spectrum must necessarily go from no harm at all to absolute harm, and that any position *before* the current harm is necessarily *less harmful* than the current harm itself. Similarly, if one has the means to alleviate the present harm—“...*thwarting, defeating, or setting back of some party's interests...*” (Beauchamp & Childress, 2013, p. 153)—and despite all, chooses to do nothing, then they are equally morally responsible for the present harm as the original cause of such harm. This means that if you have the means to alleviate the harm to someone—let us say their current harm sits at 10 on a hypothetical scale ranging from 0 (no harm) upwards—and you decide to do nothing, then you not only maintain the status quo and share moral responsibility for that harm, but also for any further escalation that may follow until annihilation of the individual, whether this might be complete loss of dignity of the individual, sense of Self or death.

By not addressing the present harm therefore one is not only responsible for the present state but also for its proliferation. To deny such premises means to deny the fact that one's existence and actions can alter the course of events. It is to imply that mere awareness of a harmful state does not in any way interact with, or alter, such a state.

“...if it is in our power to prevent something bad from happening, without thereby sacrificing anything of comparable moral importance, we ought, morally, to do it. By “without sacrificing anything of comparable moral importance” I mean without causing anything else comparably bad to happen, or doing something that is wrong in itself, or failing to promote some moral good, comparable in significance to the bad thing that we can prevent. This principle seems almost as uncontroversial as the last one. It requires us only to prevent what is bad, and not to promote what is good, and it requires this of us only when we can do it without sacrificing anything that is, from the moral point of view, comparably important.”
(Singer, 1972, p. 231)

Awareness of suffering therefore transforms the bystander into a moral agent—one who now has both knowledge and capacity, and therefore responsibility. To fully grasp the above except, it is necessary to single out and analyse its most critical part, namely the idea of *anything of comparable moral importance*.

What Is at Stake: Suffering, Dignity, and Moral Responsibility

In the context of MAiD or BID, what is at stake in both cases is *suffering* and *dignity* (for example Chochinov et al., 2002; Hurst, 2003; Rodríguez-Prat et al., 2016). Although both terms are conceptually volatile and shift across philosophical, clinical, and cultural frameworks, for the present discussion they can be taken in the following empirically grounded sense:

“...dignity is distinctive in that it also has an external component based on the perception of one’s worthiness of honour and esteem from others. This is consistent with the proposed dignity model, which sees dignity mediated via internal, bodily (dignity conserving repertoire and illness-related concerns, respectively), and external factors (social dignity inventory).” (Chochinov et al., 2002, p. 441)

“Suffering encompasses the biological, social, psychological, and spiritual dimensions of severe illness, yet has personal meaning for each individual.

Suffering is most often mentioned in connection with pain, yet they are not synonymous because suffering can occur in pain's absence. For example, severe depressive disorder rarely causes physical pain, yet results in enormous suffering. Illness can be uncomfortable and distressing, but does not always cause suffering. Suffering is not just a sum of one's symptoms."(Ganzini et al., 1999, p. 1434)

This means that if, by intervening, I increase suffering and/or further jeopardise the patient's dignity, then I should refrain from acting; however, if, by the same token, suffering is diminished or completely removed and dignity is preserved or improved, then I ought to act.

The delicate point now is to assess whether the death of the patient can be considered a valid means of removing suffering. After all, death is final, and a good argument might be that by killing the patient—although intentions are good, and we are respecting the patient's wishes—we are not removing the suffering from the patient, but rather we are removing the patient altogether from being able to experience anything at all (Hanser, 2012). Such a comparison risks sounding extreme—akin to dropping an H-bomb on a country to eliminate a single terrorist cell or employing machine guns to clear a garden of a mole infestation. There is, however, an escape from such a putative impasse.

"...an event is on balance bad for someone if and only if his life would have been on balance better had that event not occurred... A person's actual death, then, is bad for him if and only if his life would have gone better had that death not brought it to an end. Of course, if the person hadn't died that death, he would have died some other death instead—none of us is immortal. But if his life would have gone better had he died that other death instead of his actual one, then his actual death is bad for him." (Hanser, 2012, p. 1)

From here, it follows that death is bad for a person when it deprives them of future well-being they would otherwise have enjoyed. Such a formulation necessarily recalls the potentiality argument on the abortion debate, which speculates that a being is harmed by being killed because it is deprived of the goods it *would* have experienced in its future, even if it is not currently experiencing them:

“...What primarily makes killing wrong is neither its effect on the murderer nor its effect on the victim's friends and relatives, but its effect on the victim.... [it] deprives one of all the experiences, activities, projects, and enjoyments that would otherwise have constituted one's future.” (Marquis, 1989)

Having the potential to experience goods, however, is not morally equivalent to actually having interests, desires, or capacities. Mary Anne Warren explicitly argues such a point, stating that the mere potential to become a person does not confer the rights of a person

“...whatever the rights of potential people may be, they are invariably overridden in any conflict with the moral rights of actual people.” (Warren, 1973, p. 2)

Although Warren's argument concerns the rights of actual persons versus the rights of merely potential (non-existent) persons, the structural point is still useful here. A hypothetical future self—whose values, capacities, or identity conditions may never materialise—functions, for present moral reasoning, much like a merely potential person: it has no standing to override the claims of the actual, presently existing subject, especially when the present subject's decisions are deliberated and exercised in autonomy. This does not deny the relevance of ordinary future interests; rather, it applies only when the imagined *future self* would not be a continuous moral subject—for example, when the individual would no longer possess the capacities that constitute personhood, or when the projected interests of that future state run directly against the present person's deliberate and well-considered autonomous judgement. This means that moral speculation shall not privilege the hypothetical interests of a future version of the patient when such interests conflict with those of the patient in their present state. To do so would be to subordinate the actual moral claims of the person—or a past person, if the person's wishes were expressed before a debilitating state that hinders their medical decision-making capacity in the present moment—to the speculative claims of a merely possible future self whose desires and values may never materialise. A person, in this context, is meant as a being with intrinsic capacities—*personhood*—that is, a being possessing characteristics such as consciousness, reasoning ability, self-motivated activity, capacity to communicate, and self-awareness (Warren, 1973, p. 5).

Before concluding this section, one further point must be noted: situations may arise in which suffering and dignity appear mutually exclusive, with the alleviation of one threatening the other. How such cases should be approached is taken up in the following section, through the distinction between critical and experiential interests.

Critical and Experiential Interests

To further reinforce the point previously made—that the hypothetical or potential interests of a future version of the patient should not override the actual interests, desires, or capacities of the patient in their present state—it is possible to use two additional arguments. The first is the hypothetical distinction between *critical interests* and *experiential interests*.

“...We need the distinction between experiential and critical interests to understand many of our convictions about how people should be treated. ... Understanding the difference between experiential and critical interests is also essential to understanding a certain kind of tragedy ... when someone looks back on his life, near the end, and finds it wasted, empty of any real significance. ... Many people, as I said, think it undignified or bad in some other way to live under certain conditions, however they might feel if they feel at all. ... At least part of what people fear about dependence is its impact not on those responsible for their care, but on their own dignity. ... Whether it is in someone’s best interests that his life end in one way rather than another depends on so much else that is special about him—about the shape and character of his life and his own sense of his integrity and critical interests—that no uniform collective decision can possibly hope to serve everyone even decently.” (Dworkin, 2011, pp. 227–238)

What Ronald Dworkin proposes with this distinction is that not all the reasons someone might have for valuing their life can be reduced to moment-to-moment pleasures and pains. Experiential interests—such as enjoying a good meal, listening to music, or feeling the sun on one's face—do matter as they are pleasurable. However, critical interests are markers of deeper commitments to certain life-shaping values that determine whether one regards their life, taken in its entirety, as having been worthwhile. These may include maintaining one's dignity, completing important projects, or living in a way that expresses one's convictions. For

the present reasoning on MAiD, it implies that the decision about living or dying—such as euthanasia or PAS—often might hinge more on critical interests than experiential ones. A person might still derive some pleasure from simple experiences yet judge that continuing to live in a state of total dependency would betray their sense of self or diminish the narrative integrity of their life.

It is possible to illustrate the argument with an example. Imagine a mountain climber, someone who has lived all their life among the peaks of the highest mountains, someone who has built their own sense of life's worth around physical challenge, self-reliance, and being in harmony with the surrounding nature. Now imagine that the same mountain climber suffers a severe accident and becomes quadriplegic, bound for life to a bed, and dependent on others for basic care. While such an individual might still find enjoyment in listening to music or conversing with friends—experiential interests—they could feel their life no longer aligns with their values, whether this might be self-reliance, physical mastery, or deep meditations among solitary mountain peaks. Such critical interests are what they believed made their life worth living. Such a person might choose MAiD not as a way to reject life per se, but as a way to preserve their dignity in a way aligned with what their critical interests demand. This is to say that such a mountain climber might choose to end their life for a few related reasons such as to preserve their sense of Self as a mountain climber and to fulfil their life narrative on their own terms. In doing so, they seek to retain that sense of Self and avoid the slow erosion of dignity and self-conception through the physical constraints and illnesses that would reduce them to a bedridden relic of their former self. It is a way to maintain cohesion with a life lived according to one's own term, and nothing can be more dignifying than that; it is a worthy conclusive chapter to a nicely written book.

Now it is important to make a necessary remark. We are not talking here of the life of the paraplegic per se. But we are talking about the mountain climber's life. Such a remark it is essential to avoid being accused to consider the quadriplegic life not worth living by default. That is not the claim being made here. Rather it is possible to anticipate such accusation by introducing the second point that reinforces the idea that the hypothetical or potential interests of a future version of the patient should not override the actual interests, desires, or capacities of the patient in their present state. This second point is the nature of the alternative at the disposal of the individual.

“The impact on one’s well-being will likely depend on the nature of the alternative chosen. If such a choice is inferior to the first, then it is feasible to speculate that there will be a decline in one’s well-being. Conversely, if the second-choice activity turns out to be better, in some regards, than the initial choice, it will increase well-being.” (Loriga, 2025a, p. 101)

Well-being means what “...encompasses all the ways in which people experience and evaluate their lives positively.” (Tov, 2018, p. 1). The point, therefore, is straightforward: the value of a person's life depends on the alternatives they envision for themselves in the long run. If the alternatives available after a significant change are perceived as being of lesser value—failing to compensate for the loss of their life's former critical interests, as described in the previous account—then that life may lose much of its meaning for the person. Conversely, if such alternatives are seen as replacing, or even adding value to the critical interests that were abruptly taken away, then life may remain, or even become, worth living. Let us revisit the mountain climber example once more.

Imagine that, after the accident, the individual interprets the event as an opportunity to redirect their life toward pursuits that align with new, yet equally meaningful, critical interests—such as mentoring young climbers, writing about mountaineering, or advocating for environmental preservation in alpine regions. In this case, the accident, while tragic, becomes a pivot point toward a life that still reflects a coherent narrative of self and purpose (see, for example, the Dax Cowart's case Gerrek, 2018).

A potential counterargument to this reasoning, however, might be the following: how can the individual truly know whether a future alternative will be able to compensate for what has been lost? A straightforward answer to that is they cannot know with certainty—but neither can the medical community, the family, or any other party. All perspectives share this fundamental uncertainty. Yet, among all these positions of uncertainty, the individual necessarily occupies a privileged standpoint when it comes to assessing their own future. This is because they alone possess the intimate, first-person knowledge of their life history, values, commitments, and the narrative arc that gives their existence coherence. Only they can judge whether a proposed alternative can be integrated into that narrative in a way that preserves its meaning and integrity. Outsiders may observe the facts, but they cannot supply the lived significance that only the subject can access.

BID and MAiD: Dignity Beyond Death

The idea that dignity must be preserved throughout all life stages and not only within MAiD discourse seems obvious. BID, however, seems to be sitting outside such reasoning, and not necessarily without good reasons. BID is, in fact, in a peculiar position; medically recognised and yet without any therapeutic approach. The only approach that appears successful in alleviating the dysphoric sensation in the long run is amputation (see, for example, Blom et al., 2012, 2014), which is highly controversial and currently unavailable in most Western jurisdictions. The available data supporting it are too limited in size to justify its adoption from a statistical standpoint—a consequence of the domino effect mentioned earlier (in the short run interesting results emerged for example with the application of Virtual Reality models as reported by Saetta et al., 2025). From a statistical perspective, the post-amputation variables remain numerous and largely indeterminate such as post-amputation regret, the onset of phantom pain, the recurrence of new amputation desires, and all further interventions needs that might arise from comparable surgical procedures. In addition to clinical uncertainties, social implications must also be considered, including financial responsibility for both surgery and post-operative care in the event of complications—in other words, who shall pay for surgery and all that may come next?—as well as the eligibility of such individuals for disability pensions. The social—and financial—aspect of the phenomenon, as already mentioned, will not be addressed here—although amply done elsewhere (Loriga, 2025a). Rather, the focus will be on one aspect only, which can be summarised in the following: is it better to attempt surgery in the first place or deny the procedure in the hope for a future, non-invasive and potentially reversible type of procedure which might never even happen? In other words, is it better to let the harm endure with its potential snowball effect, or act now with the risk of patient regret, complication and all that might come next?

By framing BID in such a way, it is evident how the reasoning developed previously for MAiD now becomes relevant. What is at stake, once again, is suffering and dignity. Rather than attempting to address each clinical uncertainty by itself—which in any case will remain unresolved within the medical community due to the absence of robust statistical data—the discussion can be shifted toward the moral dimension by returning to the example proposed in the previous section. To place the reasoning on solid ground, it is necessary first to establish a postulate: the individuals under consideration are those who have been legitimately

recognised by medical professionals as having BID. This is not to imply that individuals without a formal diagnosis must be excluded a priori; however, if one wishes to operate within the framework of a specific medical setting, it is necessary to adhere to its rules. A formal diagnosis thus becomes essential in order to remove any doubt, from a medical standpoint, that the individual in question indeed has BID. The next step is to frame BID as a life-threatening condition (Loriga, 2025a, p. 33), not only because of the plunge in quality of life, but also due to the risk of DIY solutions when the dysphoria reaches its highest intensity.

“...Labelling the desire for amputation as irrational overlooks the fact that, in this context, rationality involves seeking relief from suffering rather than enduring it. The apparent rationality of the desire for amputation in BID might become obscured when the desire reaches its peak intensity. If likened to a wave, the individual might be driven to extreme actions when the wave is at its highest point. Conversely, rationality is more likely preserved when the wave is at its lowest. Like a wave, the cycle of the BID desire from crest to trough affects its intensity and, consequently, the rationality of the desire.” (Loriga, 2025a, p. 72)

What is at stake in the case of BID is precisely what is at stake in MAiD: the possibility of bringing harm to an end rather than prolonging that suffering in the uncertain hope of future solutions that may never materialise. In other words, the need to prioritise the interests of the present individual, aligned with the narrative life-path that the individual envisions for themselves, and not the interests of a speculative future self whose existence remains uncertain.

In the case of BID, compelling individuals to continue in such circumstances inevitably affects both their social relationships and their sense of self, preventing them from realising their full potential. It entails a devaluation of life, rendering the individual disposable—reduced to a mere *omissis*, a placeholder that glides over the intrinsic meaning of the action—abstention—it is a moral fallacy. Such abstention rests on the faulty assumption that non-intervention constitutes the lesser harm compared to intervention: that potential future clinical complications are more severe than the current situation, and that by refusing to act one is thereby relieved of moral responsibility. This assumption is false. As per the case of MAiD, once one becomes aware of the issue and possesses the means to alleviate suffering,

one also becomes morally accountable not only for the present harm but also for all subsequent consequences. In MAiD, as in BID, abstention means the prolongation of suffering, the erosion of dignity, and potentially the loss of the sense of self. Yet BID introduces a further risk—namely, the death of the patient, as it might be for DIY solutions attempted at the peak of dysphoria, such as lying on train tracks in an attempt to chop off the unwanted body part. For BID, here death is not the goal—as it might be for MAiD—but rather an unwanted consequence of desperation. The question, therefore, is not only about managing post-operative complications, but of determining the trajectory of an entire life: whether it is better to force the individual to endure a well-established harm—and risk DIY approaches—or to respect personal autonomy and dignity and permitting surgery in accordance with the individual’s own life narrative-path.

Conclusion

It is now time to draw a conclusion of what has been proposed so far. The present paper argued that BID shall be everybody's concern because, despite its apparent oddity, it puts a spotlight on matters of dignity and autonomy, which all individuals must care about as perishable beings. A few important points were proposed that now necessitate reiteration.

The first point is that knowledge confers moral responsibility. It follows that abstention from action is an illusion, a lullaby for conscience. Once awareness of suffering enters one’s sphere of consciousness, the choice to do nothing is itself a morally charged act. By becoming aware of a harm, one not only becomes responsible for that very harm but also for the future possible harm originating from that present harm state.

It is like saying that if you know, for example, that a traffic light positioned at a busy intersection is faulty, and you could have it quickly fixed by ringing the local authorities—who in the meantime, let us say, may deploy some nearby policemen to control traffic—you are already responsible for the danger that traffic light poses if you choose not to act. Similarly, if, on top of not calling the local authorities, you also decide to stand still with your arms crossed, and watch drivers bolt through the green traffic light—when in fact, you know that the traffic light should have been red—without giving them any warning, you are morally blameworthy for that inaction as well. In this analogy, the traffic light represents the initial harm (n=10) that could have been quickly fixed by calling the local authorities—the harm for which you become responsible by the very fact of knowing about

it. The car crashes and all their victims and injured parties, in turn, represent the greater harm (say $n=15$, to remain consistent with the previous section) that flows from the originating harm. Failing to amend the first harm so that it will overflow toward the second greater harm makes you even more blameworthy.

Within the context of MAiD, this means that there is indeed a meaningful moral difference between active euthanasia—killing—and passive euthanasia—letting die—but not in the classic sense, which holds that letting die is morally preferable to killing. On the contrary, the reasoning advanced here reverses that assumption and positions the passive aspect as the more morally blameworthy one.

To further support this idea, a second point was introduced: the distinction made between experiential and critical interests. Experiential interests refer to momentary pleasures, while critical interests define the deeper commitments that make one's life coherent and worthwhile, as might be, for example, preserving dignity and a sense of self through a defined type of identity associated with a specific lifestyle, as per the mountain climber example. In both MAiD and BID, decisions are not about short-term pleasures but about whether one's critical interests can still be realised. For the individual facing a MAiD decision, the critical interest may lie in concluding life in accordance with their own life plan. For the individual with BID, by contrast, it may lie in beginning life anew—without the burden of dysphoric desire. In both cases, dignity might be otherwise eroded away.

This leads to the third point; life depends not simply on what is lost, but on the alternatives that remain available. If the alternatives following a significant change are qualitatively inferior to what has been lost—failing to replace or sustain the critical interests that once gave life coherence—then well-being and dignity decline. Conversely, if new alternatives can equal or surpass in quality what was lost, life may regain—or maintain—value. In BID the question is whether meaningful alternatives exist that enable the individual to sustain a coherent life narrative and preserve dignity. For those with BID, the available alternatives are limited: enduring suffering, resorting to dangerous DIY solutions, or pursuing medical intervention (currently unavailable). Among these, medical intervention appears indeed the least harmful, as it at least offers the possibility of a medically controlled relief—surgery—rather than the certainty of deterioration. In the case of MAiD, by contrast, when no such meaningful alternatives remain, death itself may constitute the most dignified option, a deserving final chapter to a life already well lived.

This paper is not, of course, a call for unsupervised amputations for anyone claiming to have BID, nor for the indiscriminate euthanising of all those wishing point-blank to do so. Nor is it the purpose of this paper to propose specific medical policies or procedural guidelines. The paper aimed, above all, to demonstrate the moral inconsistency within which BID currently sits. Dignity is not something that shall be taken into question only when it comes to end-of-life decision-making. It is something that must be considered and fostered throughout the life of the individual, despite the oddities that might entail. Until the medical community will confront the BID phenomenon with the same seriousness as MAiD, individuals with BID will remain in a state of epistemic and clinical exile—acknowledged as subjects of suffering but not recognised as agents of their own fate. It is in this sense that BID surgery parallels active euthanasia, while the refusal of BID surgery parallels passive euthanasia. In both cases, harm is present; yet while passive euthanasia and the refusal to amputate may appear to represent the lesser harm, they preserve a status quo that can trap the individual in prolonged suffering until complete demise—understood not necessarily as physical death, but as the erosion of the sense of self and of all that one has been held dear up to that moment. By contrast, active euthanasia—and, by analogy, surgical intervention in BID—may in fact constitute the more compassionate course of action when it respects the patient’s wishes.

This is exactly why we should all care about BID in the same way as why we should all care about MAiD, and why it is necessary to recognise that abstention is not inaction, nor is it neutrality. Caring about BID means caring not only about a medical oddity and the people affected by it, but also and above all about human dignity. It is to recognise that anyone may one day find themselves in a similar situation—if not in the present, then in the final stages of life—and that having one’s wishes respected is a way out of a painful prison that can strip away dignity through suffering and the fragmentation of self. The point here is not that we live in a mutually supportive system—or at least we like to think we do—but that refusing to engage with certain topic postpones the necessary reckoning that all of us must eventually face; the possibility to be trapped in a body that you no longer recognise as yours, in a life that does not respect you anymore. That is, indeed, to silently fade away without dignity.

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